

Transient Thermal Modeling of Thermoplastic Composite Filament Winding Process

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Thermosetting Vs Thermoplastic Composite Filament Winding

Applications of Thermoplastic Composite Filament Winding Process

Fuselage structures

Hydrogen Tanks

Deep submarines

Transient State Thermal Model (static-non linear heat transfer problem)

Problems related to Thermoplastic Composite FW Process

- Polymer Degradation
- Incomplete Consolidation
- Residual Stresses
- Voids

$$\rho C \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + v_z \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \omega \frac{\partial T}{\partial \theta} \right) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(K_r r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(K_\theta \frac{\partial T}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K_z \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right)$$

FEM Implementation Scheme

Parametric numerical study of the effects of winding velocity and heating power on the temperature and stress distribution

- In all the layers: The maximum temperature increased with lower winding velocity.
- Higher maximum temperature on the second layer.
- Larger heat diffusion area is observed on the third layer.

- In all the layers: The maximum temperature increased with increasing heating power.
- Higher maximum temperature on the second layer.
- Larger heat diffusion area is observed on the third layer.

- Higher positive stress at the center of the boundary and compressive stress at the immediate areas.
- Higher stress resulted with increasing heating power.
- Edge effects at the free ends and vary with heating power.